

THE UNIQUENESS OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL CULTURAL COMPETENCES IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract. This article talks about the specifics of developing general cultural competencies of future educators.

Key words: social, competency, spiritual, method, goal, educator, subculture.

INTRODUCTION

Pre-school education as the primary link of primary education is the main issue recognized by our state. President Sh. In M. Mirziyoev's lecture entitled "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility - should be the rule of every leader's activity", it was stated that the coverage of children in preschool education is only 27 percent, and the work in this field is It was noted that it was neglected.

Based on these tasks, great work is being done in our country in order to improve the quality of preparing children for school education. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH. The decision of M. Mirziyoev "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" is proof of these opinions.

In our republic, great changes are being made in terms of further improvement of the preschool education system, paying special attention to children's education from an early age.

It is known that the development of large-scale socio-economic, national-cultural relations with the peoples of different countries in the current era of globalization and intercultural communication has increased the interest of young people in acquiring universal competencies.

The organization of perfect personality education has been an important requirement and main goal of society in all eras. Naturally, even in the conditions of current educational reforms, well-rounded personality education is gaining importance. The socio-economic, spiritual and educational changes taking place at the current stage of society's development require the fundamental reform of the education sector, its complete liberation from the ideological views and prejudices left over from the past, at the level of developed democratic states, high spiritual and moral requires training of highly qualified, modern personnel who meet the requirements and improving efficiency by improving the educational process.

There may be more or less people in the world, but there are no more or less nations in the cultural and spiritual sphere. Each nation has its own past, cultural and spiritual values, national heroes, traditions that should be recognized by others, and signs of blood brotherhood. In this regard, universality consists of preserving the values of all nations and peoples, respecting those that the balance of history preserves, and realizing that the diversity of national values in the world is inextricably linked with natural diversity.

It is appropriate to use the following methods in the development of general cultural competence of educators of preschool educational organizations:

Conversation in problematic description. This type of interview is carried out with educators in an analytical and research way. The following conditions must be taken into account when organizing a question-and-answer session:

a) the questions are based on the information that educators have imagination;
b) questions do not require answers limited to mechanical reworking of what was read;

c) pay attention to the interrelation of the contents of the questions.

It is possible to carry out conversations with a number of problematic descriptions related to the education of universal competences.

1. In the process of developing communicative competence, the following problematic questions can be used:

Why do people feel the need to communicate?

What qualities should a person have in order to listen carefully to the opinions of others?

☑ in what situations do you find it difficult to listen to the opinion of your interlocutor?

☑ why are some people unable to accept opposing views?

Do you have to be the same age to be friends?

☑ can two people be friends if they don't like each other?

☑ can friends lie to each other?

☑ What qualities do you appreciate in your interlocutor?

☑ What do you mean by etiquette?

What Eastern thinkers do you know about speech etiquette?

2. In the process of developing national competencies, attention should be paid to solving the following problematic questions:

a) in what aspects is the universal importance of national culture manifested?

b) Is cultural diversity positive or negative?

c) can subculture be accepted as a value? (subculture Latin. sub - "ost" is a term of sociology, anthropology, cultural studies, which means a sharply differentiated part of the society's culture. Within the subculture, there may be specific clothing, slang, behavior and other cultural norms).

g) How is loyalty to the country manifested in people?

d) the role of being kind to people in our lives?

e) Explain belief in universal and national values.

o) How do you understand the pedagogue's dress code and cultural norms?

j) How much do you follow a healthy lifestyle in your lifestyle?

3. In the course of conversations related to the development of international tolerance, the following problematic questions may be presented:

a) Why is it necessary to treat representatives of other nations with respect?

b) What is the necessity of learning the language, culture, customs of representatives of other nations and being able to accept them?

c) Explain the concepts of "national pride" and "nationalism".

4. In order to develop the competence of a socially active citizen, it is possible to address the educator with the following problematic questions during the interview process:

a) What is the feeling of belonging to the events and processes happening in the society?

b) How to actively participate in the events taking place in society?

c) What are the civil duties and rights of the educator and to what extent do you follow them?

g) How do you interpret the behavior and observance of legal culture in labor and civil relations?

5. The following problematic questions can be used in the process of developing the competence of self-development as a person:

a) What should be done for the educator to constantly develop himself physically, spiritually, mentally, intellectually and creatively?

b) To what extent is it important for an educator to strive for perfection, independent study throughout life?

c) How do you interpret the alternative assessment of one's behavior?

g) What is the role of being able to make independent decisions in a person's life? Can you make independent decisions in any situation? Whose opinion do you rely on when making decisions (yourself, your parents, teachers, supervisors, friends, others)?

CONCLUSION

Along with the formation of national qualities such as "national pride", "national decency", "national ideological consciousness" in a person based on general cultural competences, the qualities of tolerance, inter-ethnic harmony, solidarity and tolerance also grow. Nationality in these qualities is directly connected with the process of realizing a person's national identity. As a result, the national feeling of the young generation is not spontaneous, but is directed and served to the goals of national independence and creativity. It protects national pride from nationalism, localism, indifference to one's people, and arrogance.

So, based on general cultural competences, the knowledge collected and improved by a certain nation or people during historical development, which includes the ideas of bringing children to maturity and forming national qualities in them, is passed from generation to generation.

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